

Ligand-imposed Structural Features of Transition Metal Complexes with Heterocyclic Benzoylhydrazones

SAYAJI RAO and K. HUSSAIN REDDY*

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003

Manuscript received 16 November 1995, revised 27 February 1996, accepted 14 May 1996

Copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of some benzoylhydrazones, viz. furyl-2-methylketone benzoylhydrazone (FMBH) and thiophene-2-methylketone benzoylhydrazone (TMBH) have been synthesised. The molar conductivity data show them to be non-electrolytes. The tridentate nature of the ligands is inferred from ir spectral studies. The magnetic moment values together with electronic spectral data suggest an octahedral structure for all the complexes. Various esr parameters for copper complexes have been calculated.

In recent years there has been growing interest in the chemistry of aroylhydrazones¹ derived from ketones with heterocyclic moiety containing ring oxygen and ring sulphur atoms. So far no attempt has been made for the synthesis and characterisation of transition metal complexes of furyl-2-methylketone benzoylhydrazone (FMBH, I) and thiophene-2-methylketone benzoylhydrazone (TMBH, II)². It led us to study the copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of FMBH and TMBH, which have ONO and ONS donor sequence respectively.

X = O, I (FMBH)
X = S, II (TMBH)

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of 2×10^{-5} M solutions of ligands were recorded at various pH values. The pK_a values for the deprotonation of FMBH and TMBH have been calculated from the variation of absorbance with pH by the reported method³ and are found to be 4.7 and 5.6 respectively.

The ¹H nmr spectra of FMBH and TMBH in CDCl₃ show signals respectively at δ 11.35 and 11.75 ppm assigned to imino protons and at δ 2.38 and 2.30 ppm due to methyl protons. Mass spectra of FMBH and TMBH show molecular ion peaks at m/z 228 (5) and 244 (20) respectively. Other important peaks are observed at m/z 67 (5, 10), 77 (78, 50) and 105 (100, 100) due to the formation of C₄H₃O⁺, C₆H₅⁺ and C₆H₅CO⁺ fragments respectively. The

ir spectra of FMBH and TMBH show absorption bands respectively at 3 229, 3 230 (NH) and 1 630, 1 638 cm⁻¹ (C=N) suggesting the Schiff base formation.

The complexes of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Co^{II} (Table 1) are crystalline solids, soluble in chloroform, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide, but insoluble in water, methanol and ethanol. The molar conductivities of $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions of the complexes in DMF were found in the range 5–15 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹ indicating their non-electrolytic nature⁴. The analytical data support the 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) composition of the complexes. The magnetic moment values of the copper complexes suggest the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for monomeric copper(II) complexes. The magnetic moments of the nickel complexes of FMBH and TMBH (2.9 and 2.7 B.M. respectively) are in favour of octahedral geometry with ³A_{2g} ground state term symbol⁵. The magnetic moments of cobalt(II) complexes also support the octahedral geometry.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE LIGAND AND COMPLEXES*

Compound	Colour	M.p ** °C	μ_{eff} B.M.
FMBH	Brown	143–45	–
Cu(FMB) ₂	Dark green	263–65	2.2
Ni(FMB) ₂	Brown	240–42	2.9
Co(FMB) ₂	Red	171–73	4.0
TMBH	Yellow	197–99	–
Cu(TMB) ₂	Green	238–40	2.0
Ni(TMB) ₂	Greenish brown	180–82	2.7
Co(TMB) ₂	Reddish brown	179–81	4.5

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

** Metal complexes decomposed in the range indicated.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of Cu(FMB)₂ and Cu(TMB)₂ complexes exhibit broad bands at 15 870 and 16 000 cm⁻¹ respectively, with shoulders at 14 000 and 14 830 cm⁻¹, which are assigned respectively to ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} transitions in a tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry. Charge transfer bands (L → M) in the spectra of the complexes in chloroform

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF THE COBALT AND NICKEL COMPLEXES

Compd.		ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	B	$\delta\nu^*$	B_{35}^{35}	$10 Dq$	$(\nu_2-\nu_1)$	ν_2/ν_1	LFSE
Ni(FMB) ₂	Observed	9 435	16 395	25 000	—	—	—	9 435	6 960	1.73	26.95
	Calculated		15 402	25 991	872	±993	0.84	9 435	5 967	1.63	—
Ni(TMB) ₂	Observed	9 090	15 875	22 220	—	—	—	9 090	6 783	1.74	25.97
	Calculated		14 525	23 560	721	+1 350	0.70	9 090	5 435	1.60	—
Co(FMB) ₂	Observed	—	15 387	17 390	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Calculated	7 185	15 382	17 384	746	-16	0.77	8 189	8 197	2.14	23.42
Co(TMB) ₂	Observed	—	15 625	17 240	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Calculated	7 249	15 480	16 950	712	-290	0.73	8 230	8 231	2.13	23.51

*Difference in the observed and the calculated values.

** Ratio of the free ion and of the complex.

solution are observed at *ca.* 26 500 cm⁻¹.

The electronic spectra of the paramagnetic nickel(II) complexes exhibit three bands (Table 2) in support of an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion. These bands are attributable to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν_1); ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν_2) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) (ν_3) transitions respectively. The spectral bands are utilised to compute important ligand field parameters using the ligand field theory of spin-allowed transitions in d⁸ configuration⁶. The values of 10 Dq and Racah interelectronic repulsion parameters (B) are employed to calculate ν_2 and ν_3 (Table 2) leading to the following conclusions. Comparison of 10 Dq and B values for the complexes indicates that the ligands give reasonably strong fields and form strong covalent bonds. The high values of Dq and B are also consistent with coordination of azomethine nitrogen. The ratio of ν_2/ν_1 lies in the range 1.60–1.74 expected for octahedral nickel(II) complexes⁷; the usual range being 1.50–1.76 for octahedral symmetry.

The higher LFSE values of Ni(FMB)₂ in comparison to Ni(TMB)₂ suggest the presence of stronger interaction between the metal ion and FMB, possibly due to the coordination of furan oxygen in axial position.

The electronic spectra of Co(FMB)₂ and Co(TMB)₂ complexes show two distinct bands at 15 387, 15 625 cm⁻¹ (ν_2) and 17 390, 17 240 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) attributable to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{1g}(P) transitions respectively, in an octahedral field. Racah interelectronic repulsion parameters (B), covalent factor (B₃₅) and 10 Dq values were calculated using standard equations⁶. Using 10 Dq and B, the value of ν_1 was calculated,

$$\nu_1 = 5 Dq - 7.5 B + 1/2(225 B^2 + 10 Dq^2 + 180 DqB)^{1/2}$$

The ratio, ν_2 observed/ ν_1 calculated, was found to be in the range 2.13–2.14 as required for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁶.

Esr spectra : Anisotropic spectra obtained for Cu(FMB)₂ and Cu(TMB)₂ complexes in dimethylformamide at liquid nitrogen temperature, reveal four peaks of small intensity, considered to originate from g_{II} component. The spin Hamiltonian, orbital reduction and bonding parameters of all the complexes are presented in Table 3.

The g_{II} values suggest the covalent character⁹ of the metal-ligand bond in the complexes. The G values of these complexes are greater than four, suggesting the absence of interaction between two copper centres. The α^2 values also support the covalent nature of the present complexes¹⁰. The values of p are also consistent with the covalent bonding of copper to oxygen atom¹¹.

TABLE 3—SPIN HAMILTONIAN AND ORBITAL REDUCTION PARAMETERS OF THE COPPER COMPLEXES

Parameter	Cu(FMB) ₂	Cu(TMB) ₂
g _{II}	2.273	2.260
g _L	2.063	2.053
g _{av}	2.133	2.122
G	4.46	5.08
A _{II} (cm ⁻¹)	0.013 5	0.014 0
A _L * (cm ⁻¹)	0.001 8	0.001 4
A _{av} (cm ⁻¹)	0.005 7	0.005 6
K _{II}	0.805	0.785
K _L	0.762	0.697
α^2	0.843	0.840
P	0.019	0.020
K	0.580	0.398

Infrared spectra : Important ir bands of ligands and their complexes are presented in Table 4. The presence of ν_{NH} band in the spectra of FMBH and TMBH suggest that the ligands exist in keto form in the solid state. However, in solution and in the presence of metal ions, the ligands may exist in equilibrium with tautomeric enol form which can act as a singly charged ligand. The bands appearing in the spectra of FMBH and TMBH respectively, at 1 660, 1 650; 1 630, 1 638; 1 534, 1 533; 1 013, 1 023 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$, ($\beta_{NH} + \delta_{C-N}$) and ν_{N-N} modes respectively. Strong bands present in the spectra of FMBH and TMBH at 708 and 610 cm⁻¹ respectively, are assigned to the furan and thiophene ring deformation modes¹².

Ir spectra of the metal chelates lack absorption due to both ν_{NH} and $\nu_{C=O}$, instead they show new bands characteristic¹³ of ν_{N-CO} around 1 310 cm⁻¹ suggesting the enolisation of keto group and bonding of the ligand through enolate oxygen. The red-shift of the ring deforma-

TABLE 4—SELECTIVE IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF LIGANDS AND THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν _{NH}	Amide-I		Amide-II		ν _{M-O}	ν _{M-N}
		ν _{C=O}	ν _{C=N}	[β _{N-H} + δ _{C-N}]	ν _{N-N}		
FMBH	3 229	1 660	1 630	1 534	1 012	—	—
Cu(FMB) ₂	—	—	1 620	1 520	1 025	568	400
Ni(FMB) ₂	—	—	1 615	1 515	1 028	585	490
Co(FMB) ₂	—	—	1 615	—	1 029	520	450
TMBH	3 230	1 649	1 639	1 533	1 013	—	—
Cu(TMB) ₂	—	—	1 619	1 517	1 029	546	420
Ni(TMB) ₂	—	—	1 619	1 524	1 025	568	482
Co(TMB) ₂	—	—	1 629	1 517	1 028	530	460

tion vibrations in the spectra of the metal complexes suggests the participation of furan oxygen and thiophene sulphur in coordination. In the far-ir region, additional bands are observed at 530–580 (M–O) and 400–490 cm⁻¹ (M–N)^{14,19}.

Based on molar conductance, magnetic and spectral data, octahedral structure is suggested for the complexes irrespective of the nature of metal ion present.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared¹⁵ by refluxing 1 : 1 molar (0.05 mol) quantities of a suitable ketone with benzhydrazide in methanol for 2 h.

CuCl₂, NiCl₂·6H₂O and CoCl₂·6H₂O were used. An aqueous solution of the metal salt (0.02 mol) was added to the ligand (0.02 mol) in methanol (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 2–6 h. The crystalline complexes which separated out were washed with hot water and methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

The elemental analyses were performed at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian XL spectrometer (300 MHz), mass spectra on a Fanning Mat 8230 spectrometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-112 X band spectrometer at liquid nitrogen temperature in dimethylformamide. Molar conductance of complexes in DMF (~10⁻³ M) was determined at 27 ± 2° using a Systronic 303 conductivity bridge and magnetic susceptibility using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) operating at a field strength of 2–8 kG.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank C.D.R.I., Lucknow and R.S.I.C.s, Bombay and Madras for providing elemental analysis and spectral data respectively.

References

- H. K. DUGGAL and D. V. AGGARWAL, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1988, **18**, 87; R. L. DUTTA and Md. M. HOSSAIN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1984, **23**, 130; B. SINGH, R. N. SINGH and R. C. AGGARWAL, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Organ. Chem.*, 1984, **14**, 815.
- R. L. DUTTA and Md. M. HOSSAIN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1985, **44**, 635; S. RAO, Ph.D. Thesis, S. K. University, 1995.
- J. P. PHILLIPS and L. L. MERRITT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 410.
- M. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **7**, 81.
- B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Interscience, New York, 1960, p. 220.
- A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1984.
- M. L. CARLIN, "Transition Metal Complexes", 4th. ed., Marcel Dekker, New York, 1968.
- E. KONIG, "The Nephelauxetic Effect, Structure and Bonding", Springer, New York, 1971, p. 175.
- D. KIVELSON and R. NEIMAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.
- K. L. REDDY, S. SRIHARI and P. LINGAIAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 801.
- G. GIORDANO and R. D. BEREMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 1019.
- K. M. IBRAHIM, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1991, **28**, 327; C. L. JAIN and P. N. MUNDLEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **33**, 993.
- N. K. SINGH and R. TRIPATHI, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1988, **13**, 346.
- C. NOBORU and K. NAKAMOTO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **10**, 798; K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978.
- S. RAO and K. H. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 681